

CIGS SOLAR CELL MANUFACTURED BY USING NEW SELENIZATION METHOD

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1 Introduction

Solar cells based on the $Cu(In,Ga)Se_2$ (CIGS) compound semiconductor have recorded the highest conversion efficiency among thin film solar cells technologies. Among many processes to synthesize high quality CIGS absorber, so far, vacuum methods are known to have higher perfection for mass production technology. Especially, the 2-step process consisted of the precursor deposition and subsequent thermal processing under the selenium atmosphere, has been known for its advantage in producing large area modules. The selenization process normally uses H_2Se gas owing to its high chemical reactivity, however, its severe toxicity and corrosiveness requires additional safety facilities. While the use of Se vapor evaporated from elemental Se source is relatively free from the safety issue, it suffers from the difficulty of uniform supply over the large area and its low reactivity.

In this paper, a new Se supply method using a Se-covered glass (SCG) is proposed to overcome the problem of using Se vapor. In the SCG selenization, a Se-coated sodalime glass (SLG) plate is closely placed on a metal precursor face to face. This method is designed to provide uniform Se flux over a large area metal precursor.

2 Experimental

Precursors were deposited on 500nm Mo coated sodalime glass substrate by magnetron co-sputtering system. RF and DC power were supply $CuGa(20at\%)$ and In target respectively. $Cu/(In+Ga)$ ratio of precursor was about 0.9 and it had 600nm thickness. Composition and thickness were measured Inductively Coupled Plasma and alpha-step each. The SCG was made by using a thermal

evaporator. Thickness of Se was varied over 0.6 ~ 3.0 μm . Selenization process was done in two-zone quartz furnace. Atmosphere in the reaction chamber was N_2 gas in 1atm, ramp up speed was $20^\circ C/min$ and reaction time was 60min on $500^\circ C$.

Crystallography of CIGS layer was analyzed by XRD. Raman scattering was used for reliability of XRD data and confirm existence of binary phase. Surface and cross section morphology were observed by FE-SEM. [1-2]

3 Results and discussion

Fig. 1. XRD data of selenised precursor by verified Se thickness SCG method. (a) 0.6 μm , (b) 1.0 μm , (c) 1.8 μm , (d) 3.0 μm

Fig 1 is the result of XRD pattern about CIGS that selenised by SCG. The typical CIGS peaks including (112)/(103), (204)/(220) and (116)/(312) were observed for all the Se thicknesses. However, $MoSe_2$ peak intensity became stronger as Se was thicker. In the thickest Se, Fig 1-(d), Mo peak intensity was very weak and $MoSe_2$ peak was so strong.

Fig. 2. Raman spectrum about CIGS depends on Se thickness.

Result of the Raman spectrum, Fig 2, proves existence of CIGS phase. Existence of CIGS and MoSe₂ appeared at 183cm⁻¹ and 240cm⁻¹ each. Broad peak at 220cm⁻¹ was believed to be InSe, however, it's hard to decide because there was B2/E signal of CIGS. Peak of Cu_xSe₂ was not detected.

Fig. 3. Data of CIGS solar cell applied SCG method.

CdS and TCO were deposited on the CIGS that fabricated SCG method. Data of solasimulator was shown fig 3. It play Eff.=2.93%, JSC=21.55mA/cm², VOC=0.33V, F.F= 41.2%.References

4. Reference

[1] S. Yamanaka, M.Konagai and K.Takahashi,

“Characterization of Copper Indium Diselenide

Thin Films by Raman Scattering Spectroscopy for Solar Cell Applications”, Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.,

Vol. 28. pp. L1337-L1340, 1989

[2] Satoshi Yamanaka, Masayuki Tanda, Nobuyuki

Nakada, Akira Yamada, Makoto Konagai and

Kiyoshi Takahashi, “Study of CuInSe₂

Formation Kinetics in the Selenization Process

by Raman Spectroscopy”, Japaness Journal of

Applied Physics, Vol. 30. pp. 442-446, 1991